

KASB HUNAR MAKTABLARINING FIZIKA FANIDA “TOK MANBAINING ELEKTR YURITUVCHI KUCHI VA ICHKI QARSHILIGINI ANIQLASH.” LABORATORIYA ISHI MAVZUSINI PHET.COLORADO.EDU DASTURI YORDAMIDA O‘QITISH METODIKASI

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Anotatsiya. Ushbu maqola kasb-hunar maktablarida raqamli texnologiyalar vositasida fizika fanida “Tok manbaining elektr yurituvchi kuchi va ichki qarshiligini aniqlash.” laboratoriya ishi mavzusyolgulnoza ini Phet.colorado.edu dasturi yordamida o‘qitish metodikasiga bag‘ishlangan bo‘lib, ta‘limda kompyuter dasturlaridan dars mashg‘ulotlarida foydalanishning ahamiyati amaliy yoritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: raqamli texnologiya, tok manbalarining elektr yurituvchi kuchi, Phet.colorado.edu, ichki va tashqi qarshilik, Laboratoriya universal tok manbai yoki akkumulyator, ampermetr, voltmeter, kalit

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена теме «Определение электрической движущей силы и внутреннего сопротивления источника тока» по физике с помощью цифровых технологий в профессиональных учебных заведениях. Лабораторная работа посвящена методике преподавания программы Phet.colorado.edu и практически объяснена важность использования компьютерных программ в образовании.

Ключевые слова: цифровая техника, источники электрического тока, Phet.colorado.edu, внутреннее и внешнее сопротивление, лабораторный универсальный источник тока или аккумулятор, амперметр, вольтметр, переключатель.

Abstract. This article is "Determining the electric driving force and internal resistance of a current source" in physics with the help of digital technologies in vocational schools. The laboratory work is devoted to the teaching methodology of the Phet.colorado.edu program, and the importance of using computer programs in education is practically explained.

Key words: digital technology, electrical current sources, Phet.colorado.edu, internal and external resistance, Laboratory universal current source or battery, ammeter, voltmeter, switch

Darsning mavzusi: Laboratoriya ishi: Tok manbaining elektr yurituvchi kuchi va ichki qarshiligini aniqlash.

Darsning rejasi:

1. Laboratoriya ishi bilan tanishish.
2. Laboratoriya ishini bajarish.

Darsning maqsadi: O‘quvchilarning ampermetr va voltmeter yordamida tok manbaining elektr yurituvchi kuchini va ichki qarshiligini aniqlash haqidagi bilim, ko‘nikma va malakalarni shakllantirish.

O‘tgan mavzuni takrorlash

O‘tilgan mavzularni takrorlash va o‘quvchilarning eslash qobiliyatini tekshirish maqsadida “Xotira” mashqi o‘tkaziladi.

Buning uchun o‘quvchilar kichik guruhlarga ajratiladi va ekranda har xil qonunlariga doir suratlar formulalar, iboralar, so‘zlar ko‘rsatiladi. Tasvirlar tugagach guruhlarning har biriga mavzu beriladi va har bir guruh o‘ziga berilgan mavzu bo‘yicha ma’lumotlarni eslab qog‘ozga tushuradi. Quyida ushbu tasvirlar ko‘rsatilgan.

	$\mathcal{E} = I \cdot R + I \cdot r = U_R + U_r$		
$W_{el} = \frac{qU}{2}$		Amper	
	$I = q/t$	$\mathcal{E} = A_{ch}/q$	$j = \frac{I}{S}$
Galvanik element		$B = \frac{M_{max}}{N \cdot I \cdot S}$	
$q = I_{o'rc} \cdot t$	$I_{q,t} = \mathcal{E}/r$		(A).
	$I_{o'rc} = \frac{I + I_0}{2}$	$1 \text{ V} = 1 \text{ J}/\tilde{1} \text{ C}$	
$F_A = I \cdot B \cdot l.$	$j = nq_0 v$	$I = \mathcal{E}/(R+r)$	
$A_1 = mgh$	I_0	A_{ch}	I
	$\varphi = \frac{W_p}{q_0}$	$\vec{E} = \frac{\vec{F}}{q_s}$	

Yangi mavzu bayoni

O'qituvchi "Elektrostatik maydon" tushunchasini tushuntirish uchun Phet.colorado.edu saytiga kiradi va mavzuga doir simulyatsiyalar orqali ma'lumotlarni tushuntiradi. Buning uchun quyidagi havolani ustiga sichqonchani olib kelinadi va chap tugma 2 marta bosiladi.

<https://phet.colorado.edu/en/simulations/circuit-construction-kit-dc-virtual-lab?locale=uz>

Ekkranda quyidagi oyna hosil bo'ladi (1-rasm).

1-rasm.

Boshlash tugmasini bosamiz va kerakli laboratoriya jihozlarini tanlaymiz.

Kerakli asboblari: Laboratoriya universal tok manbai yoki akkumulyator, ampermetr, voltmetr, kalit, ulovchi simlar, 10 Ω va 20 Ω qarshilikka ega bo'lgan rezistorlar (2-rasm).

2-rasm.

Ishni bajarish tartibi

1. Rasmda keltirilgan elektr zanjirini yig'ing (3-rasm). Zanjirga 10 Ω qarshilikli rezistorni ulang.

2. Kalit ochiq holda voltmetr ko'rsatishi U_V ni yozib oling. 4-a rasm. $U_V = \mathcal{E}$ ga teng deb oling.
3. Kalitni ulang va ampermetr ko'rsatishi I_A ni yozib oling. 4-b rasm.
4. Natijalarni 1-jadvalga ko'chiring.

1-jadval

No	U_V , (V)	U_2 , (V)	I_A (A)	R (Ω)	r , Ω
1	9	6	0.6	10	5
2	9	7.2	0.36	20	5

5. Tok manbaining ichki qarshiligini formuladan hisoblang va natijani jadvalga ko'chiring.

$$I = \frac{\mathcal{E}}{R+r}; \quad \mathcal{E} = U_V; \quad I_A = \frac{U_V}{R+r}; \quad r = \frac{U_V - I_A R}{I_A};$$

6. Zanjirga 20Ω qarshilikli rezistorni ulang va tajribani takrorlang 5-rasm. a) kalit ochiq b) kalit yopiq.

a)

b)

5- rasm. a) kalit ochiq b) kalit yopiq

7. 1- va 2-tajribada topilgan r_1 va r_2 larni solishtiring.

Yangi mavzuni mustahkamlash

Yangi mavzuni mustahkamlash uchun o'quvchilar ushbu loabaratoriya ishini 15Ω va 30Ω qarshilikka ega bo'lgan rezistorlar uchun qayta bajarishadi va olgan xulosalarini tushuntirib beradi.

Uyga vazifa

Quantum physics va Crocodil kabi vertuval laboratoriya dasturlaridan foydalangan holatda Tok manbaining elektr yurituvchi kuchi va ichki qarshiligini aniqlash.

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